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Mr Jean-Pierre Bourguignon
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CONCERNS: Full support for open access to scientific publications and implementation of Plan S in Horizon Europe

DATE: 20 August 2020

Dear Ms Gabriel, Mr Paquet and Mr Bourguignon

Recalling our [recent position Open Access in Horizon Europe](#), the leading universities of science and technology united in [CESAER](#) remain strong supporters of open science and open access to scientific publications.

We value the leadership that the European Commission and the European Research Council (ERC) have shown on these important topics, including in their support of [Plan S](#) which we also fully support.

It was therefore with surprise that we learned of the ERC Scientific Council's [abrupt withdrawal](#) of their support from Plan S, despite their support since its inception, which was also [reiterated](#) last year.

With this letter, I reiterate our association's strong support for achieving full and immediate open access. We firmly believe that Plan S is an important step towards achieving this goal, as expressed in our [position Open Access in Horizon Europe](#).

We call upon the European Commission to continue their leadership in open science and open access, and we look forward to the full implementation of Plan S in the model grant agreement for Horizon Europe.

Please do not hesitate to contact us if you have any questions, or if we can provide any further support and constructive input.

Yours sincerely

Rik Van de Walle
President of CESAER
Rector of Ghent University